

PERIODIC SOLUTIONS OF THE SYSTEM OF
NONLINEAR DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS AND
THEIR PROPERTIES

Muhammadiyev Zohidjon Hasan o'g'li

Termiz State University

2nd year graduate student

Abstract: This article presents information about the system of nonlinear differential equations, the sequence of systems of equations.

Key words: system of nonlinear differential equations, matrices, fixed numbers, periodic functions.

Let's consider the system of non-linear differential equations.

$$x(t + 1) = A x(t) + F(t, x(t), y(t)), \quad (2.1.1)$$

$$y(t + 1) = B y(t) + \Phi(t, x(t), y(t)),$$

Here A, B are constant numbers, $p \times p$ and $q \times q$ are matrices, $F(t, x, y)$, $\Phi(t, x, y)$ are continuous vector functions, $t \in \mathbb{R}$.

Now

$$A = \text{diag}(A_1, \dots, A_n), \quad B = \text{diag}(B_1, \dots, B_n)$$

Here A_i, B_j are $p_i \times p_i$ and $q_i \times q_i$ matrices, respectively

$$A_i = \begin{pmatrix} a_i & \varepsilon & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & a_i & \varepsilon & \dots & 0 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & \varepsilon \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & a_i \end{pmatrix} \quad B_j = \begin{pmatrix} b_j & \varepsilon & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & b_j & \varepsilon & \dots & 0 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & \varepsilon \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & b_j \end{pmatrix}$$

Here

$$\sum_{i=1}^r p_i = p, \quad \sum_{j=1}^s q_j = q, \quad \text{and } \varepsilon \text{ is a sufficiently small positive number.}$$

Let's assume that the following conditions are met

$$1) \quad |a_i| < 1 < |b_j|, \quad i = 1, \dots, r, \quad j = 1, \dots, s;$$

2) Vector functions $F(t, x, y), \Phi(t, x, y)$ are continuous in $t \in \mathbb{R}, x \in \mathbb{R}^p, y \in \mathbb{R}^q$, periodic in $T - t$ and satisfy the Lipschitz condition.

$$|F(t, x', y') - F(t, x, y)| \leq \mu(|x' - x| + |y' - y|),$$

$$|\Phi(t, x', y') - \Phi(t, x, y)| \leq \mu(|x' - x| + |y' - y|),$$

Here

$$|x| = \max_{1 \leq i \leq p} |x_i|, \quad |y| = \max_{1 \leq i \leq q} |y_i|, \quad x', x \in \mathbb{R}^p, \quad y', y \in \mathbb{R}^q,$$

μ is a sufficiently small positive number.

Theorem 2.1.1. If the following conditions are met

1) $|a_i| < 1 < |b_j|, \quad i = 1, \dots, r, \quad j = 1, \dots, S;$

2) $F(t, x, y), \Phi(t, x, y)$ vector functions $t \in \mathbb{R}, x \in \mathbb{R}^p$

is continuous in $y \in \mathbb{R}^q$, periodic in $T - t$ and satisfies the Lipschitz condition.

Then there is a continuous T -periodic solution $(v(t), w(t))$ of the system of equations (2.1.1).

Proof: Consider the sequence of systems of equations.

$$\begin{aligned} x_m(t+1) &= Ax_m(t) + F(t, x_{m-1}(t), y_{m-1}(t)), \\ y_m(t+1) &= By_m(t) + \Phi(t, x_{m-1}(t), y_{m-1}(t)), \end{aligned} \quad m=1, 2, \dots$$

(2.1.2)

Here $x_0(t)=0, y_0(t)=0$.

It is easy to check that the system of equations (2.1.2) has formal solutions in sequence form for any $m \geq 1$.

$$x_m(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} A^{i-1} F(t-1, x_{m-1}(t-i), y_{m-1}(t-i))$$

(2.1.3)

$$y_m(t) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} B^{-(i+1)} \Phi(t+1, x_{m-1}(t+i), y_{m-1}(t+i))$$

We show that the series (2.1.3) smoothly converges to some continuous T -periodic functions $x_m(t), y_m(t)$ for all $t \in \mathbb{R}$.

$$|x_m(t)| \leq \frac{M}{1-\lambda} \quad |y_m(t)| \leq \frac{M}{1-\lambda}, \quad (2.1.4)$$

Here

$$M > \max\{M_1, M_2\}, \quad M_1 = \max_t |F(t, 0, 0)|,$$

$$M_2 = \max_t |\Phi(t, 0, 0)|, \quad 1 > \lambda > \max\{|a_i|, |b_j^{-1}|, i = 1, \dots, r, j = 1, \dots, s\}.$$

Indeed, it was known that $m=1$

$$x_1(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} A^{i-1} F(t-1, 0, 0)$$

$$y_m(t) = - \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} B^{-(i+1)} \Phi(t+1, 0, 0)$$

and for sufficiently small ε

$$|A| = \max_{1 \leq i \leq p} \left| \sum_{j=1}^p a_{ij} \right| \leq \lambda, \quad |B^{-1}| \leq \lambda.$$

In that case

$$|A^{i-1} F(t-1, 0, 0)| \leq M_1 \lambda^{i-1},$$

$$|B^{-(i+1)} \Phi(t+1, 0, 0)| \leq M_1 \lambda^{i+1},$$

And therefore (2.1.3) the series converges to the continuous functions $x_1(t), y_1(t)$ on $m=1$ and all $t \in R$ by T-period

$$|x_1(t)| \leq M_1 \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \lambda^{i-1} \leq \frac{M_1}{1-\lambda},$$

$$|y_1(t)| \leq M_2 \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \lambda^{i+1} \leq \frac{M_2}{1-\lambda},$$

Then in this case

$$|x_m(t)| \leq \frac{M}{1-\lambda} \quad |y_m(t)| \leq \frac{M}{1-\lambda}$$

relations will be appropriate.

Similarly, we can prove the convergence of the series (2.1.3) and the correctness of the hypothesis (2.1.4) for $m=2,3,\dots$. Let us assume that the convergence of the

series (2.1.3) and the validity of the assumption (2.1.4) have already been proved for $m > 2$, and we will consider the series.

$$x_{m+1}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} A^{i-1} F(t-i, x_m(t-i), y_m(t-i))$$

$$y_{m+1}(t) = - \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} B^{-(i+1)} \Phi(t+1, x_m(t+i), y_m(t+i))$$

Because

$$|x_{m+1}(t)| \leq \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} |A|^{i-1} |F(t-i, x_m(t-i), y_m(t-i)) - F(t-1, 0, 0)|$$

$$+ \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} |A|^{i-1} |F(t-1, 0, 0)|,$$

$$|y_{m+1}(t)| \leq \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} |B^{-1}|^{i+1} |\Phi(t+i, x_m(t+i), y_m(t+i)) - \Phi(t+1, 0, 0)|$$

$$+ \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} |B^{-1}|^{i+1} |\Phi(t-1, 0, 0)|,$$

1), 2) we get the following result according to the conditions

$$|x_{m+1}(t)| \leq \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \lambda^{i-1} \mu \left(\frac{M}{1-\lambda} + \frac{M}{1-\lambda} \right) + M_1 \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \lambda^{i-1} \leq 2 \frac{M_1}{(1-\lambda)^2} \mu + \frac{M_1}{1-\lambda} \leq$$

$$\leq \frac{M}{1-\lambda} \left(\frac{M_1}{M} + 2 \frac{\mu}{1-\lambda} \right)$$

$$|y_{m+1}(t)| \leq \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \lambda^{i+1} \mu \left(\frac{M}{1-\lambda} + \frac{M}{1-\lambda} \right) + M_2 \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \lambda^{i+1} \leq \frac{2M}{(1-\lambda)^2} \mu + \frac{M_2}{1-\lambda} \leq$$

$$\leq \frac{M}{1-\lambda} \left(\frac{M_2}{M} + \frac{2\mu}{1-\lambda} \right)$$

For sufficiently small positive numbers μ

$$\frac{M_1}{M} + \frac{2\mu}{1-\lambda} \leq 1, \quad \frac{M_2}{M} + \frac{2\mu}{1-\lambda} \leq 1.$$

Thus, the sequence (2.1.3) smoothly converges to periodic continuous functions $m > 1$ and $t \in R$ (2.1.4) satisfying assumption (2.1.4) in $m > 1$ and $t \in R$.

Now we prove the sequence of vector functions.

$\{x_m(t)\}, \{y_m(t)\}$ sequences $x(t), y(t)$ smoothly approach continuous periodic vector functions and satisfy the system of equations (2.1.1).

For this, it is enough to show that the following relations hold for all $m > 1$ and $t \in R$

$$\|x_m(t) - x_{m-1}(t)\| \leq \frac{M}{1-\lambda} \lambda^{m-1}, \quad (2.1.5)$$

$$\|y_m(t) - y_{m-1}(t)\| \leq \frac{M}{1-\lambda} \lambda^{m-1},$$

here $\|x(t)\| = \max_t |x(t)|, \quad \|y(t)\| = \max_t |y(t)|$

We know that $m=1$

$$|x_1(t) - x_0(t)| \leq \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} |A|^{i-1} |F(t-i, 0, 0)| \leq \frac{M_1}{1-\lambda},$$

$$|y_1(t) - y_0(t)| \leq \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} |B^{-1}|^{i+1} |\Phi(t+i, 0, 0)| \leq \frac{M_2}{1-\lambda}$$

And based on that,

$$\|x_m(t) - x_{m-1}(t)\| \leq \frac{M}{1-\lambda} \lambda^{m-1}, \quad (2.1.5)$$

$$\|y_m(t) - y_{m-1}(t)\| \leq \frac{M}{1-\lambda} \lambda^{m-1},$$

the relationship holds for $m=1$.

Using the conditions of the sequence (2.1.3) and the theorem, we can see that our hypothesis (2.1.5) is valid for $m=2,3,\dots$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |x_{m+1}(t) - x_m(t)| \\
 & \leq \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} A^{i-1} |F(t-i, x_m(t-i), y_m(t-i)) - F(t-i, x_{m-1}(t-i), y_{m-1}(t-i))| \\
 & \leq \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \lambda^{i-1} \mu (|x_m(t-i) - x_{m-1}(t-i)| + |y_m(t-i) - y_{m-1}(t-i)|) \\
 & \leq \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \mu \lambda^{i-1} 2 \frac{M}{1-\lambda} \lambda^{m-1} \leq \\
 & \leq \frac{M}{1-\lambda} \lambda^{m-1} \frac{2\mu}{1-\lambda},
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |y_{m+1}(t) - x_m(t)| \\
 & \leq \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} B^{i+1} |\Phi(t+i, x_m(t+i), y_m(t+i)) - \Phi(t+i, x_{m-1}(t+i), y_{m-1}(t+i))| \\
 & \leq \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \lambda^{i+1} \mu (|x_m(t+i) - x_{m-1}(t+i)| + |y_m(t+i) - y_{m-1}(t+i)|) \\
 & \leq \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \mu \lambda^{i+1} 2 \frac{M}{1-\lambda} \lambda^{m-1} \leq \\
 & \leq \frac{M}{1-\lambda} \lambda^{m-1} \frac{2\mu}{1-\lambda},
 \end{aligned}$$

Bizda $\frac{2\mu}{1-\lambda} \leq \lambda$ ma'lum edi

$$|x_m(t) - x_{m-1}(t)| \leq \frac{M}{1-\lambda} \lambda^m,$$

$$|y_m(t) - y_{m-1}(t)| \leq \frac{M}{1-\lambda} \lambda^m.$$

And, therefore, assumptions (2.1.5) are also valid for $m+1$.

This proves that relations (2.1.5) hold for all $m \geq 1$ and $t \in \mathbb{R}$. Taking into account the following relations (2.1.5), the sequence of vector functions $\{x_m(t)\}, \{y_m(t)\}$

$v_m(t)$ is smooth to some continuous T -periodic vector functions $v(t), w(t)$ we come to the conclusion that it approaches. If we calculate the limit of (2.1.2) in $m \rightarrow \infty$, then it is easy to show that $v(t), w(t)$ is a solution of the system of equations (2.1.1).

Suppose that there is one more continuous periodic solution of the system of equations (2.1.1) $(\tilde{v}(t), \tilde{w}(t))$ and $v(t) \neq \tilde{v}(t), w(t) \neq \tilde{w}(t)$ be. Because $v(t) = Av(t-1) + F(t-1, v(t-1), w(t-1))$,

$$B^{-1}w(t+1) = w(t) + B^{-1}\Phi(t, v(t), w(t)),$$

and

$$\tilde{v}(t) = A\tilde{v}(t-1) + F(t-1, \tilde{v}(t-1), w(t-1)),$$

$$B^{-1}\tilde{w}(t+1) = \tilde{w}(t) + B^{-1}\Phi(t, \tilde{v}(t), \tilde{w}(t)),$$

ago

$$|v(t) - \tilde{v}(t)| \leq |A||v(t-1) - \tilde{v}(t-1)| + \mu(|v(t-1) - \tilde{v}(t-1)| + |\tilde{w}(t) - \tilde{w}(t-1)|),$$

$$\begin{aligned} |w(t) - \tilde{w}(t)| &\leq |B^{-1}||w(t+1) - \tilde{w}(t+1)| \\ &+ \lambda\mu(|v(t) - \tilde{v}(t)| + |w(t) - \tilde{w}(t)|). \end{aligned}$$

It implies that

$$\left| |v(t) - \tilde{v}(t)| \right| \leq \frac{\mu}{1-\lambda-\mu} |w(t) - \tilde{w}(t)|,$$

$$\left| |w(t) - \tilde{w}(t)| \right| \leq \frac{\mu}{1-\lambda-\mu} \left| |v(t) - \tilde{v}(t)| \right|, \quad \text{Or}$$

$$\left| |v(t) - \tilde{v}(t)| \right| \leq \frac{\mu^2}{(1-\lambda-\mu)^2} \left| |v(t) - \tilde{v}(t)| \right|,$$

$$\left| |w(t) - \tilde{w}(t)| \right| \leq \frac{\mu^2}{(1-\lambda-\mu)^2} \left| |w(t) - \tilde{w}(t)| \right|$$

Since we have $2\mu/(1-\lambda) < 1$, it follows that $0 < \mu/(1-\lambda-\mu) < 1$, and so,

$$\begin{aligned} \left| |v(t) - \tilde{v}(t)| \right| &\leq 0, & \left| |w(t) - \tilde{w}(t)| \right| &\leq 0, \\ v(t) &= \tilde{v}(t), & w(t) &= \tilde{w}(t). \end{aligned}$$

The resulting result shows that the solution is the same as $(v(t), w(t))$.

The theorem is proved.

(2.1.1) by making the following changes

$$x(t) = \tilde{x}(t) + v(t), \quad y(t) = \tilde{y}(t) + w(t) \quad (2.1.6)$$

We get the following system of equations.

$$\tilde{x}(t + 1) = A \tilde{x}(t) + \tilde{F}(t, \tilde{x}(t), \tilde{y}(t)), \quad (2.1.7)$$

$$\tilde{y}(t + 1) = A \tilde{y}(t) + \tilde{\Phi}(t, \tilde{x}(t), \tilde{y}(t)),$$

Here

$$\tilde{F}(t, \tilde{x}, \tilde{y}) = F(t, \tilde{x}(t) + v(t), \tilde{y}(t) + w(t)) - F(t, v(t), w(t))$$

$$\tilde{\Phi}(t, \tilde{x}, \tilde{y}) = \Phi(t, \tilde{x}(t) + v(t), \tilde{y}(t) + w(t)) - \Phi(t, v(t), w(t)).$$

$$\tilde{F}(t, 0, 0) \equiv 0, \quad \tilde{\Phi}(t, 0, 0) \equiv 0 \quad \text{va} \quad \tilde{F}(t, \tilde{x}, \tilde{y}), \quad \tilde{\Phi}(t, \tilde{x}, \tilde{y}) \quad \text{It is easy}$$

to show that vector functions satisfy condition 2).

Therefore, the trivial solution $(\tilde{x}(t) \equiv 0, \tilde{y}(t) \equiv 0)$ is the only periodic solution of the system of equations (2.1.7). However, this system of equations can have many continuous solutions that satisfy the conditions

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \pm\infty} |\tilde{x}(t)| = 0, \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow \pm\infty} |\tilde{y}(t)| = 0$$

Therefore, from now on, we will study the existence of continuous solutions of the system of equations (2.1.7) and ways to find them, the conditions are met.

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \pm\infty} |\tilde{x}(t)| = 0, \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow \pm\infty} |\tilde{y}(t)| = 0$$

Theorem 2.1.2. Let the vector functions $\tilde{F}(t, \tilde{x}, \tilde{y})$, $\tilde{\Phi}(t, \tilde{x}, \tilde{y})$ be continuous, periodic in t and satisfy the following conditions

$$\tilde{F}(t, 0, 0) \equiv 0, \quad \tilde{\Phi}(t, 0, 0) \equiv 0,$$

$$|\tilde{F}(t, \tilde{x}', \tilde{y}') - \tilde{F}(t, \tilde{x}'', \tilde{y}'')| \leq \mu(|\tilde{x}' - \tilde{x}''| + |\tilde{y}' - \tilde{y}''|)$$

$$|\tilde{\Phi}(t, \tilde{x}', \tilde{y}') - \tilde{\Phi}(t, \tilde{x}'', \tilde{y}'')| \leq \mu(|\tilde{x}' - \tilde{x}''| + |\tilde{y}' - \tilde{y}''|)$$

here $t \in R$, $\tilde{x}', \tilde{x}'' \in R^p$, $\tilde{y}', \tilde{y}'' \in R^q$.

Then we change it as follows

$$\tilde{x}(t) = \bar{x}(t), \quad \tilde{y}(t) = \bar{y}(t) + \gamma(t, \bar{x}(t)), \quad (2.1.8)$$

where $\gamma(t, \bar{x}(t))$ is a vector function that is constant for some functions, periodic in t , and leads the system of equations (2.1.7) to the form

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{x}(t+1) &= A\tilde{x}(t) + \tilde{F}(t, \tilde{x}(t), \tilde{y}(t)), \\ \tilde{y}(t+1) &= B\tilde{y}(t) + \tilde{\Phi}(t, \tilde{x}(t), \tilde{y}(t)),\end{aligned}\quad (2.1.9)$$

Here the vector functions $\tilde{F}(t, \tilde{x}, \tilde{y})$, $\tilde{\Phi}(t, \tilde{x}, \tilde{y})$ are continuous at $t \in R$, $\tilde{x} \in R^p$, $\tilde{y} \in R^q$ Periodic at $t-t$ and the following conditions are fulfilled.

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{F}(t, 0, 0) &\equiv 0, & \tilde{\Phi}(t, \tilde{x}, 0) &\equiv 0, \\ |\tilde{F}(t, \bar{x}', \bar{y}') - \tilde{F}(t, \bar{x}'', \bar{y}'')| &\leq \delta\mu(|\bar{x}' - \bar{x}'', | + |\bar{y}' - \bar{y}''|),\end{aligned}\quad (2.1.10)$$

$$|\tilde{\Phi}(t, \bar{x}', \bar{y}') - \tilde{\Phi}(t, \bar{x}'', \bar{y}'')| \leq \delta\mu(|\bar{x}' - \bar{x}'', | + |\bar{y}' - \bar{y}''|),$$

Here $\delta = \text{const} > 0$. Proof: First the following

$$\gamma(t+1, A\bar{x} + \tilde{F}(t, \bar{x}(t), \gamma(t, \bar{x}(t)))) = B\gamma(t, \bar{x}) + \tilde{\Phi}(t, \bar{x}, \gamma(t, \bar{x})) \quad (2.1.11)$$

we show that the system of equations is continuous, has a periodic solution in $T-t$ and satisfies the following conditions

$$\begin{aligned}\gamma(t, 0) &\equiv 0 \\ |\gamma(t, \tilde{x}') - \gamma(t, \tilde{x}'')| &\leq N\mu|\tilde{x}' - \tilde{x}''|,\end{aligned}\quad (2.1.12)$$

where N is an infinitely large quantity. For this, we use the method of successive approximation, and the successive approximation is determined by the following formulas.

$$\begin{aligned}\gamma_0(t, \bar{x}) &\equiv 0, \\ \gamma_m(t, \bar{x}) &= B^{-1}\gamma_{m-1}(t+1, A\bar{x} + \tilde{F}(t, \bar{x}, \gamma_{m-1}(t, \bar{x})) - \\ &\quad - B^{-1}\tilde{\Phi}(t, \bar{x}, \gamma_{m-1}(t, \bar{x})), \quad m=1, 2, \dots\end{aligned}$$

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